

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 2

Intermediate release of ESDM-PAV runtime

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1. Introduction

This document represents an interim report describing the implementation activities carried out in the scope of the ESIWACE2 project related to the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) interface for supporting data-intensive *post-processing*, *analytics* and *visualisation* (PAV). In particular, this report summarises the activities concerning the intermediate release of the ESDM-PAV software (v1.2). The activities of this release build up on those implemented for the initial software release reported in the *Initial Release of ESDM-PAV runtime interim report* [1]. This new version includes updates and extensions to the runtime system and the related Python library and client, as well as some bug fixing. In particular, it includes (i) the support for multi-node, distributed execution, (ii) the integration of additional experiment flow control statements, (iii) additional Python interfaces for experiment execution management and monitoring, and (iv) a preliminary containerisation of the software for testing purposes. Besides the description of the implementation activities strictly related to the software components, this document also includes simple examples showing the usage of the system and some documentation for the installation and setup.

2. Software architecture

The following diagram (Figure 1) shows the ESDM-PAV design introduced in ESIWACE2 milestone *MS5.1* [2] and refined in milestone *MS4.1* [3]. As for the first version, this release supports the execution of *Ophidia* [4] operators, *Climate Data Operators (CDO)* [5] and other generic command line tools, which allow for example a preliminary integration of visualisation tools such as *ParaView* [6].

Figure 1. Refined ESDM-PAV software architecture

3. Intermediate release of the ESDM-PAV software components

The following subsections describe the state, at the time of this intermediate release, of the main components of the ESDM-PAV software and summarise the implementation activities carried out so far. Further details concerning the design can be found in milestone documents MS4.1 [3] and MS5.1 [2] as well as in the first release report [1].

3.1. ESDM-PAV Experiment Schema

In this release the *experiment schema* initially defined in [1] has been extended to include new interesting features enabling the ESDM-PAV to perform complex workflows with loops, selections and other flow control operations. The runtime presented in the next section, Section 3.2, has also been extended accordingly to support the updated schema.

The *JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)* format adopted to describe PAV experiments has been used since it represents a very flexible and human-readable way to specify tasks and related interdependencies. In particular, the JSON schema has been defined starting from the Ophidia workflow schema¹ and it provides a number of PAV-specific declarations to define tasks for post-processing, analytics and visualisation.

In summary, a generic PAV experiment consists of a list of “task” JSON objects and, for each of them, the following fields are provided:

- *name*: the name given to a specific task to identify it. It is a mandatory field and its value must be unique within the whole PAV document file (i.e., a key);
- *type*: task type (see below);
- *operator*: a mandatory field specifying the operator to be executed;
- *arguments*: an optional list of values describing the input arguments for the specified operator;
- *dependencies*: an optional list of tasks (parents) that have to be completed before the execution of this specific task (child).

The schema also includes other optional fields to specify metadata (e.g. “*abstract*”); further details about the schema and its full characterisation are reported in [1].

With respect to the previous release, where the “*type*” field was simply used to specify the tool for task execution (e.g. Ophidia or CDO), thus classifying tasks on a per-application basis, it is now possible to use the “*type*” field to identify tasks which “*control*” the flow execution through control rules, e.g., iterative loops, parallel branches and selection statements. Table 1 reports the extended set of values allowed for the field “*type*” and the corresponding meaning.

Six flow control “operators” are provided by this release of ESDM-PAV software:

- for loop statement: the “*for*” and “*endfor*” constructs can be used to declare an iterative loop, when a set of tasks (i.e., a sub-workflow) has to be executed more times during the same experiment in order to improve, for instance, intermediate approximate solutions of an iterative method. Loops can also be nested;

¹ Ophidia JSON Request Schema: http://ophidia.cmcc.it/documentation/users/appendix/json_request.html

- if-else statement (“if”, “elseif”, “else” and “endif”): these flow control constructs are used to declare a selection statement. In particular, the operator “if” can be adopted in case a sub-workflow should be executed only when a given condition is met during the execution, while the “else” construct is used when an alternative sub-workflow has to be executed if the condition is not met; the “elseif” construct is adopted in case another condition needs to be verified for the execution of the alternative sub-workflow.

Table 1. Possible task *type* values supported by the ESDM-PAV schema

Task type	The task is	The field “operator” is	Example
ophidia (default)	Ophidia operator	operator name	"type": "ophidia", "operator": "oph_importnc"
cdo	chain of one or more CDO operators	chain specification	"type": "cdo", "operator": "-remapbil,grid_file"
generic	bash command	bash command	"type": "generic", "operator": "cp", "args": "a.nc b.nc"
control	flow control operator	operator name	"type": "control", "operator": "for"

The definitions of these constructs have been inherited from the corresponding Ophidia operators², although their interfaces and implementations had to be adapted to address ESDM-PAV runtime requirements.

An interesting feature provided by the loop (“for” - “endfor”) statement is the support for “*parallel branches*”. In this case, it is assumed the sub-workflow has to be applied (i) on different input datasets or (ii) on the same dataset but using different arguments in tasks composing the sub-workflow. Hence the ESDM-PAV runtime will replicate the sub-workflow into *multiple branches* before running the experiment, with the number of branches specified before experiment execution. Of course, branches can also be executed in parallel, provided that computational resources are available. It is noteworthy that this parallel branches case is quite common in different types of analysis where multiple datasets have to be processed within the same workflow, for instance for ensemble and multi-model analysis.

Listing 1 shows an example use case of a PAV experiment in JSON format where the operators “for” and “endfor” are used to define a number of “parallel branches”, each corresponding to the application of a CDO operator to a different dataset (e.g., evaluation of the meridional mean value). The “*parallel=yes*” argument (line 13) allows the activation of the parallel branch execution mode. For each branch, the name of the input file (line 21) and the corresponding output file (line 22) are determined by the argument “*index*” of the operator “for”, so that the pairs “input_file_1.nc” and “output_file_1.nc” are related to the

² Ophidia flow control operators: <http://ophidia.cmcc.it/documentation/users/operators/index.html#workflow-management>

first branch, the pairs “input_file_2.nc” and “output_file_2.nc” are related to the first branch and so on. Note that the operator “endfor” has no arguments (line 31).

```

1  {
2      "name": "Example of parallel branches",
3      "author": "ESiWACE2",
4      "tasks":
5      [
6          {
7              "name": "Begin loop",
8              "type": "control",
9              "operator": "for",
10             "arguments": [
11                 "key=index",
12                 "counter=1:3",
13                 "parallel=yes"
14             ]
15         },
16         {
17             "name": "Apply operation",
18             "type": "cdo",
19             "operator": "mermean",
20             "arguments": [
21                 "input=input_file_{index}.nc",
22                 "output=output_file_{index}.nc"
23             ],
24             "dependencies": [
25                 { "task": "Begin loop" }
26             ]
27         },
28         {
29             "name": "End loop",
30             "type": "control",
31             "operator": "endfor",
32             "dependencies": [
33                 { "task": "Apply operation" }
34             ]
35         }
36     ]
37 }

```

Listing 1. Example of use of the parallel branches on different input datasets

Listing 2 shows another example use case of a PAV experiment where the operators “for” and “endfor” are adopted: the same dataset (named “input_file.nc”, line 21) is inputted to different CDO operators (*zonmax*, *zonmin* and *zonavg*), producing different output files (line 22). Note the use of argument “values” (line 12) to associate a different operator with each branch (line 19).

```

1  {
2      "name": "Example of parallel branches",

```

```

3     "author": "ESiWACE2",
4     "tasks":
5     [
6         {
7             "name": "Begin loop",
8             "type": "control",
9             "operator": "for",
10            "arguments": [
11                "key=index",
12                "values=max|min|avg",
13                "parallel=yes"
14            ]
15        },
16        {
17            "name": "Apply operation",
18            "type": "cdo",
19            "operator": "zon@{index}",
20            "arguments": [
21                "input=input_file.nc",
22                "output=output_file_with_{index}_values.nc"
23            ],
24            "dependencies": [
25                { "task": "Begin loop" }
26            ]
27        },
28        {
29            "name": "End loop",
30            "type": "control",
31            "operator": "endfor",
32            "dependencies": [
33                { "task": "Apply operation" }
34            ]
35        }
36    ]
37 }

```

Listing 2. Example of use of the parallel branches on different input datasets and with different operators

Finally, listing 3 reports an example of usage of the “if”, “else” and “endif” constructs to select the operation for application to the input dataset, either a CDO or an Ophidia operator. The first parameter \$1 of the workflow (line 11) is used to select the branch to be executed, whereas the second parameter \$2 represents the input file name in case of CDO (line 19), or the PID of input datacube in case of Ophidia (line 39). This example shows how a PAV experiment can be coded to support different execution paths which can then be selected at run-time according to the required processing. Note that:

- the operators “else” and “endif” have no arguments;
- the operator “endif” depends on the last task of each selection branch (line 51 and 52).

```

1     {
2         "name": "Example of selection",
3         "author": "ESiWACE2",

```

```

4     "tasks":
5     [
6         {
7             "name": "Begin selection",
8             "type": "control",
9             "operator": "if",
10            "arguments": [
11                "condition=$1"
12            ]
13        },
14        {
15            "name": "Apply CDO operation",
16            "type": "cdo",
17            "operator": "timavg",
18            "arguments": [
19                "input=$2",
20                "output=output_file.nc"
21            ],
22            "dependencies": [
23                { "task": "Begin selection" }
24            ]
25        },
26        {
27            "name": "Else",
28            "type": "control",
29            "operator": "else",
30            "dependencies": [
31                { "task": "Begin selection" }
32            ]
33        },
34        {
35            "name": "Apply Ophidia operation",
36            "type": "ophidia",
37            "operator": "oph_reduce",
38            "arguments": [
39                "cube=$2",
40                "operation=avg"
41            ],
42            "dependencies": [
43                { "task": "Else" }
44            ]
45        },
46        {
47            "name": "End selection",
48            "type": "control",
49            "operator": "endif",
50            "dependencies": [
51                { "task": "Apply CDO operation" },
52                { "task": "Apply Ophidia operation" }
53            ]
54        }
55    ]
56 }

```

Listing 3. Example of use of “if”, “else” and “endif” constructs

3.2. ESDM-PAV Runtime

The ESDM-PAV runtime environment handles the management and execution of PAV experiments coded with the ESDM-PAV schema discussed in Section 3.1; it translates the JSON code into the related graph-based representation (*Directed Acyclic Graph - DAG*) and submits the tasks composing the graph at runtime, based on their dependencies. A more detailed description is reported in the first release document [1].

This version of the ESDM-PAV runtime has been further improved to:

- manage the experiment execution more effectively, and also provide the status of each task composing the experiment workflow;
- address the execution of the PAV experiments distributed over multiple nodes.

Moreover, besides these major points, the new release also includes bug fixes and other improvements in the setup phase (described in Section 4). The new ESDM-PAV runtime system release is available on *GitHub*³.

Concerning the first point, the runtime system provides the means to monitor the general status of the experiment execution and of each task associated with it. The status information can be accessed from the ESDM-PAV Python module (see Section 3.3) to verify the progress of the experiment execution. As previously mentioned, the core of the runtime is based on the Ophidia server Workflow Management System, so the definition of the status has been reprised and adapted from the Ophidia code. In particular, the status of a workflow can be as follows:

- *PENDING*: no task execution has yet begun;
- *RUNNING*: one or more tasks of the experiment are still running;
- *COMPLETED*: all tasks composing the experiment have been successfully completed;
- *ERROR*: one or more tasks composing the experiment have failed.

while similarly the task status can be as follows:

- *PENDING*: the task has been submitted but it is still waiting in its queue; in case of single-node execution, of course, this status cannot happen;
- *RUNNING*: the task is running on the computing resources;
- *COMPLETED*: the task has been successfully completed;
- *ERROR*: the task has finished with an error.

The Python module, as described in the next section, has also been extended to use the status information associated with each task, as well as the dependency information, to provide a graphical representation of the experiment execution progress.

With regards to the second main addition, a preliminary extension (still in prototypal stage) of the ESDM-PAV runtime has been implemented to support the remote execution of the tasks and to *scale* their execution on *multiple-nodes*. This extension aims to provide a higher degree of PAV experiments

³ ESDM-PAV runtime code: <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-runtime>

scalability allowing the execution (also concurrently) of the tasks composing a workflow on different nodes. Thanks to this, the current runtime version can support, based on its configuration, tasks running concurrently on the same node as well as on different nodes.

The runtime design has thus been revised to also support distributed execution scenarios. In such design, the runtime is composed of three main actors:

- the *master runtime*, the central component managing the submission of tasks that are part of the experiment, based on their dependencies;
- the *worker runtime* component, which manages the actual execution of the PAV application; multiple workers can be executed on different nodes to support concurrent execution of tasks;
- a *queuing system*, which acts as a coordinator between the two components to manage task execution.

In order to improve resource utilisation and better balance the load over the various nodes, a *pull-based* approach has been employed, i.e., each worker component will request a new task from the queueing system as soon as it becomes available after the execution of the previous task, while the master will simply place the tasks into the queue without worrying about assigning it to a specific worker.

A message queue system has been used to handle the interaction between the runtime master and worker components. Message queues are software components capable of containing messages to facilitate communication between different entities. Messages sent by sending systems are stored in queues until receiving systems consume them, so that the communication is asynchronous and managed independently by the two systems making them decoupled and easily maintainable.

The message queue system used for the ESDM-PAV is the *RabbitMQ*⁴. RabbitMQ is an open-source message-broker software created to exploit the Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) but was later extended with various plugins so that other protocols can also be used. The system provides support for fault-tolerance thanks to message recovery and allows exchanging messages in distributed applications, decoupling the communication between sender and recipient.

Figure 2 shows a high-level view of the revised ESDM-PAV runtime internal design: (i) after the experiment workflow is translated to the associated task graph, (ii) the runtime (master) submits the tasks to the queueing system in the proper order, (iii) the queueing system in turn places them in the task queue (iv) until some workers become available for the execution and queries the system for a new task, (v) once the task is assigned to the worker, it notifies its state to the runtime during the execution until its completion.

This approach allows easy horizontal scaling of the execution of experiments on multiple machines by simply starting worker components on new nodes; thanks to the pull-based solution employed, new workers can be added to the configuration without affecting the rest of the setup. It is worth noting that each worker can also run more than one task concurrently (based on the software component configuration).

⁴ RabbitMQ Documentation: Table of Contents: www.rabbitmq.com/documentation.html

The current version of the runtime is able to run only multi-threaded PAV applications, i.e., running each task on a single node on one or more cores/CPU's; support for multi-node MPI-based applications will be explored in future versions.

Figure 2. Schematisation of the ESDM-PAV runtime system internals for multi-node experiment execution

The notification system shown in Figure 2 allows the runtime to understand when a task is running, when it is completed and its exit status (either success or error). Based on this information, the runtime is able to start the execution of new (dependent) tasks and to notify the end of the workflow to the original caller.

It is important to mention that each task is associated with the execution of one of the available plugins based on the ESDM-PAV runtime master selection. There is one application-specific plugin for each tool used for the execution, so that the worker is able to transfer application-specific parameters to the tool (e.g. the number of threads for CDO operators running in multi-threading mode). See section 5 for additional details on this point.

3.3. ESDM-PAV Python Client

The ESDM-PAV Python client module allows the modeling and execution of a PAV experiment. This new version of the module extends the previous version and includes, besides bug fixes and improvements,

additional features for better experiment management and monitoring support. Inline documentation and unit testing have also been updated. The package is available on Github⁵.

The client is now able to fully support PAV experiment execution, including execution status monitoring and cancelling the execution. In particular, the principal new methods available are:

- the *cancel* method, which allows interrupting the execution of a previously submitted workflow;
- the *check* method, which validates the experiment definition for example in terms of proper syntax and dependency consistency and returns either True/False, depending on whether the workflow is valid or not and can display the experiment structure as a static graph. Thanks to this method, the user can verify the experiment structure before submitting the execution;
- the *monitor* method, providing the features to check the experiment execution progress and the status of all the tasks composing the experiment; the status can be displayed in a simple textual format or in a graphical format (Figure 4). This function also supports continuous progress monitoring (through the “*iterative*” option) by periodically updating the status visualisation at a configurable interval (“*frequency*” parameter).

Both check and monitor methods support easy integration into Jupyter Notebooks.

Listing 4 shows an example of the “*check*”, “*monitor*” and “*cancel*” methods in action: a simple experiment workflow *w1* composed of (i) a CDO regridding task (ii) followed by three independent CDO time aggregation tasks are defined in lines 3-24; before running the experiment, the check method can be used to verify its structure (line 26). The related output graph obtained from the “*check*” method is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Visualisation of the static workflow graph associated with the experiment defined in Listing 4

⁵ ESDM-PAV client code: <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-client>

```

1  from esdm_pav_client import Workflow
2
3  w1 = Workflow(name="CDO PAV experiment example",
4               author="ESiWACE2",
5               abstract="Example of PAV experiment with CDO")
6  t1 = w1.newTask(name="Regrid",
7                 type="cdo",
8                 operator='-remapbil,grid_file',
9                 arguments={'input': 'path/to/infile.nc', 'output':
10                            'path/to/outfile.nc'})
10 t2 = w1.newTask(name="Max",
11                type="cdo",
12                operator='-timmax',
13                arguments={'output': 'path/to/outfile_max.nc'},
14                dependencies={t1:'input'})
15 t3 = w1.newTask(name="Min",
16                type="cdo",
17                operator='-timmin',
18                arguments={'output': 'path/to/outfile_min.nc'},
19                dependencies={t1:'input'})
20 t4 = w1.newTask(name="Avg",
21                type="cdo",
22                operator='-timavg',
23                arguments={'output': 'path/to/outfile_avg.nc'},
24                dependencies={t1:'input'})
25
26 w1.check()
27
28 w1.submit()
29 w1.monitor(frequency=10, iterative=False, visual_mode=True)
30 w1.cancel()

```

Listing 4. Example of use of check and cancel methods

After submitting the workflow experiment *w1* (line 28), the “monitor” method can be used to get updates about the workflow progress; it takes 3 optional parameters:

- the first is the “*frequency*” parameter, an integer that determines how often the status is updated (default value is 10);
- the second is the “*iterative*” parameter (Boolean), which defines if the status has to be periodically updated (with “True”) or not (with “False”); default value is “True”;
- the final parameter is the “*visual_mode*” (Boolean). If “True” (the default value), the status will be displayed via a graph (as in Figure 4), otherwise the status will be provided by text.

In the case of Listing 4, the “monitor” method is used to get a single snapshot of the experiment status and, thus, *iterative* is set to “False” (line 29). The related execution graph is shown in Figure 4, where colors have been used to more easily identify the various task status defined in Section 3.2. In particular,

the *green* color is used for COMPLETED tasks, the *red* color for ERROR tasks, the *orange* color for RUNNING tasks and the *light orange* color for PENDING tasks; tasks not yet ready for execution are shown in *gray*. In the case displayed in the figure, all tasks have been successfully completed. Finally, while the experiment is running, it can also be easily cancelled with the “cancel” method (line 30).

Figure 4. Visualisation of the execution graph associated with the experiment defined in Listing 4

The “cancel” and “monitor” functionalities just presented have also been included in the Python command line interface (CLI), so that users can control the PAV experiment execution and status without having to implement a Python script. To this end, the CLI has also been revised to take additional options into account. The following snippet (Listing 5) shows the usage of the CLI tool for the non-blocking execution of an experiment defined in the *myexperiment.json* PAV document (line 1); the synchronous execution with status checking, through *-s option* (line 4); and then the cancellation of the experiment execution (line 8).

```

1  $ esdm-pav-client -w myexperiment.json inputarg
2  Submitted! Workflow id = 1
3
4  $ esdm-pav-client -w myexperiment.json inputarg -s
5  Submitted! Workflow id = 2
6  COMPLETED
7
8  $ esdm-pav-client -c 2
9

```

Listing 5. Example of use of the ESDM-PAV CLI

4. Installation and setup of the ESDM-PAV components

This section provides a quick reference guide for the setup of the ESDM-PAV software components: (i) the ESDM-PAV runtime and the (ii) ESDM-PAV Python client module. With respect to the previous release, the setup of the runtime has been made more automated and a preliminary effort has been carried out to improve software portability through containerisation.

4.1. Setup of the ESDM-PAV Runtime

The ESDM-PAV runtime is a C-based component and, hence, it needs to be built from source code on the target infrastructure; *GNU Autotools* (Autoconf, Automake, etc.) are used to support the building and installation phase.

In the basic, single-node setup, ESDM-PAV runtime requires a number of dependencies; before installing the code, the following packages need to be installed:

- *openssl* devel libraries
- *curl* and related devel libraries
- *libXML2* devel libraries
- *jansson* and related devel libraries
- *sqlite* and related devel libraries

For example, the following command can be used on *CentOS* Linux OS:

```
sudo yum install openssl-devel curl libcurl-devel libxml2\* jansson\* sqlite
sqlite-devel
```

In addition, *GNU Matheval* is required for the selection statement described before (in Section 3.1). Instructions to download, build and set up GNU libmatheval can be found at <http://ftp.gnu.org/gnu/libmatheval/>.

Then, the following instructions can be used to download and install the runtime from the GitHub repository:

```
git clone https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-runtime.git
cd esdm-pav-runtime
./bootstrap
./configure --prefix=$prefix --with-matheval-path=/path/to/libmatheval
make
make install
```

Before starting the runtime process, it is important to (i) create an empty SQLite database, which will be used for workflow management, and (ii) the SSL server certificates, which allow the process to operate as a remote service. The following instructions can be used to create the SQLite database:

```
cd $prefix/etc
cat esdm-pav-runtime-db.sql | sqlite3 esdm-pav-runtime-db.db
```

Certificates can be created by using the tool *openssl* and they have to be copied in the installation directory (create the directory *cert* if needed):

```
mkdir -p $prefix/etc/cert
cp cacert.pem myserver.pem $prefix/etc/cert
```

Finally, the runtime can be started as follows and it operates as a service:

```
./bin/esdm_pav_runtime
```

The process is not a daemon, but it can clearly be executed in background mode using “&”. Append option “-d” to enable verbose log in *\$prefix/log/esdm-pav-runtime.log*.

4.1.1. Setup of the ESDM-PAV Runtime multi-node version

The multi-node setup allows the run of the experiment tasks on multiple nodes concurrently as explained in Section 3.2. Besides the dependencies specified in the previous section for the software compilation, the following are also required:

- *RabbitMQ server*
- *RabbitMQ C client library*

The RabbitMQ Server can be downloaded from <https://www.rabbitmq.com/download.html>. The link also provides the instructions to install, configure and start the server instance according to the Linux distribution; for example, in case of CentOS Linux the following guide can be used: <https://www.rabbitmq.com/install-rpm.html>.

The RabbitMQ C client library, instead, is required for the interaction of the ESDM-PAV runtime with the queueing system. The following can be used to install the package from the related GitHub repository:

```
git clone https://github.com/alanxz/rabbitmq-c.git
```

Once the dependencies are installed, the multi-node version of the runtime can be installed by using the following instructions. Note that these replace the instructions in the previous section:

```
git clone https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-runtime.git
cd esdm-pav-runtime
./bootstrap
./configure --prefix=$prefix --with-librabbitmq-header-
path=/path/to/rabbitmqclib/include --with-librabbitmq-lib-
path=/path/to/rabbitmqclib/lib --with-matheval-path=/path/to/libmatheval --
enable-multi_node
make
make install
```

After these steps are completed, the instructions used for the single node installation can be used to configure the runtime master. Moreover the “*scheduler.conf*” file under the *etc* folder in the installation path should be updated according to the host information (i.e., number of cores/threads and paths). To start the various components, the following commands can be used:

```
RABBITMQ_SERVER_PATH/sbin/rabbitmq-server -detached
$prefix/bin/esdm-pav-runtime &
$prefix/bin/esdm_pav_runtime_worker &
```

The last command can be executed on each node used for the computation.

4.2. Portability of the ESDM-PAV Runtime

Portability represents an important software property that also defines how easily a software can be installed and deployed on different systems. To this end, software containers have increasingly been used by the community as a means of moving the whole software stack and its dependencies across different machines and systems [8].

In the case of the ESDM-PAV runtime, the evaluation of HPC-friendly containerisation technologies has been performed (i.e., solutions that can be deployed on HPC clusters without security and permission limitations) since the target is the execution of large-scale PAV experiments. The technology selected for this purpose is *Singularity* [9].

Hence, a preliminary containerisation of some components of the runtime software with *Singularity* has been carried out to evaluate the feasibility of the approach. In particular, the runtime master component in single-node setup has been containerised, mainly for testing purposes, and some tests of execution have been successfully completed. The full containerisation of the ESDM-PAV runtime environment will be addressed in the upcoming releases.

4.3. Installation of the ESDM-PAV Python Client

The ESDM-PAV Python client can be easily installed by using the classic Python *setuptools*. The module requires a number of Python dependencies:

- *pyophidia*
- *click*
- *graphviz*

These can be easily installed with this command:

```
pip3 install pyophidia click graphviz=0.14
```

To install the ESDM-PAV client, the following instructions can be used to download and install the module from the GitHub repository:

```
git clone https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-client.git
cd esdm-pav-client
```

```
python setup.py install
```

Alternatively, *pip* package installer can also be used within the repo folder, in place of the last command, with the following:

```
pip install -e .
```

The module can then be used as shown in the examples in Section 3.3.

5. Adaptation of PAV applications for the ESDM-PAV Runtime

The ESDM-PAV runtime supports the execution of different PAV tools, which include (i) CDO operators, (ii) Ophidia operators and (iii) generic scripts/command line tools; additional tools can be added by implementing the specific plugin.

With regards to CDO, no changes have been made to the tool: the plugin operates as a wrapper for ESDM-PAV commands (JSON tasks) to CDO operations. In this release, the interface of CDO plugin has been extended with an argument *nthreads* that can be used (at ESDM-PAV schema level) to set the number of threads to be activated for the execution of the CDO operator (in multi-threading mode). Clearly, this value is set to the parameter “-P” of the tool.

Also the plugin used to start the execution of a generic bash script (GENERIC plugin) is a simple wrapper and its implementation has not been changed in this release.

Although the implementation of the ESDM-PAV runtime is based on Ophidia Server, a number of adaptations have been made to allow the execution of Ophidia operators as ESDM-PAV applications; in particular in the module named Ophidia Analytics Framework.

First of all, the interfaces of the Ophidia operators used to convert NetCDF files into Ophidia datacubes and vice versa (e.g., *OPH_IMPORTNC* and *OPH_EXPORTNC*) have been extended to include PAV-specific arguments “*input*” and “*output*”. In this way, the description of task dependencies and how data can be transferred from Ophidia to other PAV applications (and vice versa) have been uniformed, following the schema reported above. Correspondingly, some minor modifications have also been made to the Ophidia Terminal component to consider the new arguments.

Most of the Ophidia operators access a system catalog (named Ophidia DB and implemented as a MySQL database) to retrieve information about datacubes stored in the Ophidia virtual file system: data nodes, I/O servers, fragments, etc. The system catalog also includes a number of metadata related to work sessions, workflows, jobs, registered users, etc. Clearly, this part of the catalog is not required in case Ophidia is used as a PAV application since workflow and task management is handled directly by ESDM-PAV runtime. Hence, Ophidia Analytics Framework has been adapted to enable the execution of Ophidia operators without accessing this information.

Besides extensions for the integration of Ophidia with ESDM-PAV runtime, the framework has also been integrated with the ESDM middleware through the definition of new data loading and storing operators,

such as *OPH_IMPORTESDM* and *OPH_EXPORTESDM*; this activity has been described in detail in deliverable D4.1 [7].

Finally, initial support for *in-flight analytics* has been provided to Ophidia. This feature aims to reduce the amount of data to be loaded by means of the ESDM library in case statistical information is required (maximum, minimum, average, etc.) and the operation can be offloaded to the underlying storage system, thus limiting data transfer as much as possible. Provided that the storage system is able to run the functions, *in-flight analytics* can be used to perform simple operations on large data volumes *on-the-fly* before executing more complex *kernels* within the PAV applications.

In this release, a prototype of this extension has been implemented. In particular, the operator *OPH_IMPORTESDM*, described in D4.1 [7], has been extended to load some aggregated, statistical data instead of raw data. The main changes made to the operator are summarised as follows:

- An argument *operator* has been added to *OPH_IMPORTESDM* interface to allow the selection of the statistical operation (at ESDM-PAV schema level) to be applied to data: get the maximum, the minimum or the average.
- The internal call to *esdm_read* (used to load data) has been replaced with a call to *esdm_read_stream*, thus enabling stream transfer when loading data from storage.
- The evaluation of metadata to be saved in the Ophidia system catalog has been adapted to consider the data reduction executed through *in-flight analytics*.
- The following routines have been developed to process input data and get the statistical values exploiting the ESDM Streaming API (i.e., *esdm_read_stream*). Depending on the operation to be performed, the first processes one ESDM fragment (*buff*) at a time and provides the second with synthetic data to be aggregated (*stream_func_out*): for instance, in case of the average evaluation, *stream_func_out* includes the sum and the number of valid values.

```
static void *stream_func(esdm_dataspace_t * space, void *buff, void *user_ptr, void *esdm_fill_value)
```

```
static void *reduce_func(esdm_dataspace_t * space, void *user_ptr, void *stream_func_out)
```

6. References

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